

Synthesis and spectroscopic characterization of 2,2'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline adducts of bis(μ -sulfido)bis[$\{O, O$ -dialkyl(diphenyl)dithiophosphato}oxomolybdenum(V)] complexes

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Abstract : 2,2'-Bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline adducts of bis(μ -sulfido)bis[$\{O, O$ -dialkyl(diphenyl)dithiophosphato}oxomolybdenum(V)] of the type, $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2(\phi\text{-S}_2)[\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OR})_2]_2\cdot\text{L}$ (where R = Me, Et, *i*-Pr and Ph; L = 2,2'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline) were prepared by the dropwise addition of a benzene solution of 2,2'-bipyridyl or 1,10-phenanthroline to a benzene/*n*-hexane (1 : 2) solution of bis(μ -sulfido)bis[$\{O, O$ -dialkyl(diphenyl)dithiophosphato}oxomolybdenum(V)] in equimolar ratio. The compounds, $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2(\phi\text{-S}_2)[\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OR})_2]_2\cdot\text{L}$ were characterized by elemental analysis, IR, electronic and ¹H NMR spectroscopy. If the Mo-Mo interaction is ignored, the immediate environment about Mo atoms in all compounds is essentially a distorted octahedral. The terminal oxygen atoms are in the *syn* conformation. The dithiophosphate groups are bidentate in all of the complexes.

Keywords : Molybdenum(V) complexes, dithiophosphate, dithiocarbamate, dithiocarbonate, *O, O*-dialkyl and diphenyl dithiophosphoric acids, adducts, 2,2'-bipyridyl, 1,10-phenanthroline.

Introduction

The extensive awareness in the coordination chemistry of molybdenum compounds mainly in high oxidation states with bidentate sulphur donor ligands arise in the part from the contribution of molybdenum associated with sulphur ligands in the redox-active molybdoenzymes. These molybdoenzymes catalyze two electron oxidation reduction reactions that are of vital significance in the metabolism of C, N and S by every forms of life¹⁻⁷. Oxomolybdenum complexes, with molybdenum in oxidation state (V) containing $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_3]^{4+}$ core have been reported with 1,1-dithioligands such as *N, N*-dialkyldithiocarbamates⁸⁻¹², *O*-alkyl dithiocarbonates (xanthates)¹²⁻¹⁴ and *O, O*-dialkyl(alkylene)dithiophosphates^{11,15-19}. Binuclear complexes have the $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4]^{2+}$ unit are merely known for *N, N*-dialkyldithiocarbamates²⁰⁻²³ and attempts to prepare similar complexes with *O*-alkyldithiocarbonates (xanthates)¹⁴ and *O, O*-dialkyl(alkylene)dithiophosphates²⁴ resulted in the formation of $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_3]^{4+}$ and $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}_2]^{2+}$ species, correspondingly. Compounds containing

$[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_3\text{S}]^{2+}$, $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}_2]^{2+}$, $[\text{Mo}_2\text{OS}_3]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Mo}_2\text{S}_4]^{2+}$ have been reported with dithiocarbamates²¹⁻²⁵, whereas only $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}_2]^{2+}$, $[\text{Mo}_2\text{OS}_3]^{2+}$ compounds are known with *O*-alkyldithiocarbonates¹⁴ and *O, O*-dialkyldithiophosphates²⁵. In these compounds, bridges are formed between two atoms, both being oxygen, or both sulphur or one of each. Crystal structures of several molybdenum sulphur complexes with nitrogen donor atom such as $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2(\phi\text{-S}_2)[\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OEt})_2]_2\cdot 2\text{NC}_5\text{H}_5$ ²⁴, $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2(\phi\text{-O, S})[\text{S}_2\text{P}\{\text{O}(i\text{-Pr})\}_2]_2\cdot \text{NC}_5\text{H}_5$ ²⁶ and $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2(\phi\text{-O, S})[\text{S}_2\text{P}\{\text{O}(i\text{-Pr})\}_2]_2$. Pyridazine²⁶ have been reported. In continuance for extend our knowledge of substrate binding at molybdenum centers, we depict in the present paper, the synthesis and characterization of 2,2'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline adducts of bis(ϕ -sulphido)bis[$\{O, O$ -dialkyl(diphenyl)dithiophosphato}oxomolybdenum(V)] complexes. We shall observe that the work reported in the present paper does describe probable modes of binding of 2,2'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline at unsaturated molybdenum centers, which may provide as models for biological systems.

Results and discussion

The equimolar adducts of bis(μ -sulphido)bis[$\{O, O$ -dialkyl(diphenyl)dithiophosphato}oxomolybdenum(ν)] complexes with 2,2'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline have been prepared by treatment of the oxomolybdenum(ν) complex with 2,2'-bipyridyl/1,10-phenanthroline in 1 : 1 molar ratio.

(where R = Me, Et, Prⁱ and Ph; L = 2,2'-bipyridyl, 1,10-phenanthroline)

A solution of 2,2'-bipyridyl/1,10-phenanthroline in benzene-*n*-hexane (1 : 2) was added dropwise to a solution of bis(μ -sulphido)bis[$\{O, O$ -dialkyl(diphenyl)dithiophosphato}oxomolybdenum(ν)] complexes with constant stirring at room temperature. The purple precipitate of adducts of oxomolybdenum(ν) dialkyl(diphenyl)dithiophosphates were separated, washed with *n*-hexane and dried under vacuum. These adducts are sparingly soluble in common organic solvents. Solubility increases in halocarbons (CHCl₃ and CH₂Cl₂). Unfortunately, attempts to get suitable crystals of these adducts for single crystal structure determination by X-ray diffraction were found unsuccessful.

Structure of these newly synthesized adducts have been elucidated on the base of elemental analysis (Table 1) and advanced physico-chemical techniques such as IR, UV-Visible and ¹H NMR spectroscopy.

IR spectra :

The significant assignments of IR bands (Table 2) have been made on the basis of the data for the two components of the adducts, bis(μ -sulphido)bis[$\{O, O$ -dialkyl(diphenyl)dithiophosphato}oxomolybdenum(ν)] complexes²⁴, and the coordinating moieties (2,2'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline) as well as data on bis(μ -sulphido)bis[$\{O, O$ -dialkyl(diphenyl)dithiophosphato}oxomolybdenum(ν)] complexes²¹⁻²³.

A strong band due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$, observed at 1570 cm⁻¹ in the nitrogen base ligands, is shifted to higher frequencies²⁷ by about 25 cm⁻¹ in the corresponding adducts with oxomolybdenum(ν) dialkyl(diphenyl)dithiophosphates, indicating C=N bond strengthening on adduct formation. The two strong intensity bands present in the region 850–800 cm⁻¹ and 1080–1000 cm⁻¹ are assigned to $\nu(\text{P}-\text{OC})$ and $\nu(\text{PO}-\text{C})$ stretching vibrations, correspondingly.

Two strong intensity bands in the region 972–910 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to the $\nu(\text{Mo}=\text{O})$ asymmetric and symmetric modes in oxomolybdenum(ν) complexes. A

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the 2,2'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline adducts

Compd.	Colour and decomp. temp. (C°)	Yield (%)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)	
			Metal	S
Mo ₂ O ₂ (ϕ -S ₂)[S ₂ P(OMe) ₂] ₂ ·C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂	Dark purple 340	90.57	25.02 (25.11)	23.47 (23.58)
Mo ₂ O ₂ (ϕ -S ₂)[S ₂ P(OEt) ₂] ₂ ·C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂	Dark purple 360	91.46	23.42 (23.57)	23.38 (23.58)
Mo ₂ O ₂ (ϕ -S ₂)[S ₂ P(OPr ⁱ) ₂] ₂ ·C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂	Dark purple 360	93.27	22.01 (22.05)	21.97 (21.97)
Mo ₂ O ₂ (ϕ -S ₂)[S ₂ P(OPh) ₂] ₂ ·C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂	Dark purple 360	94.05	19.03 (19.06)	19.05 (19.08)
Mo ₂ O ₂ (ϕ -S ₂)[S ₂ P(OMe) ₂] ₂ ·C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂	Dark purple 360	92.26	24.82 (24.53)	24.58 (24.54)
Mo ₂ O ₂ (ϕ -S ₂)[S ₂ P(OEt) ₂] ₂ ·C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂	Dark purple 360	90.71	22.63 (22.90)	22.82 (22.91)
Mo ₂ O ₂ (ϕ -S ₂)[S ₂ P(OPr ⁱ) ₂] ₂ ·C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂	Dark purple 310	90.57	21.24 (21.46)	21.23 (21.47)
Mo ₂ O ₂ (ϕ -S ₂)[S ₂ P(OPh) ₂] ₂ ·C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂	Dark purple 340	94.58	18.44 (18.62)	18.43 (18.64)

Table 2. Some relevant IR spectral data (cm⁻¹) for the adducts of bis(μ -sulphido)bis[$\{O, O$ -dialkyl(diphenyl)dithiophosphato}-oxomolybdenum(ν)] complexes with 2,2'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline

Sl. no.	Compd.	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{PO}-\text{C})$	$\nu(\text{Mo}=\text{O})_{\text{asym}}$	$\nu(\text{Mo}=\text{O})_{\text{sym}}$	$\nu(\text{P}-\text{OC})$	$\nu(\text{P}=\text{S})$	$\nu(\text{P}-\text{S})$	$\nu(\text{Mo}-\text{S}_2-\text{Mo})_{\text{asym}}$	$\nu(\text{Mo}-\text{S}_2-\text{Mo})_{\text{sym}}$
1.	Mo ₂ O ₂ S ₂ [S ₂ P(OMe) ₂] ₂ .C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂	1595(s)	1000(s)	955(s)	915(s)	810(s)	640(m)	540(s)	440(m)	430(m)
2.	Mo ₂ O ₂ S ₂ [S ₂ P(OEt) ₂] ₂ .C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂	1590(s)	1045(s)	972(s)	944(s)	845(s)	640(m)	535(s)	445(m)	425(m)
3.	Mo ₂ O ₂ S ₂ [S ₂ P(OPr ⁱ) ₂] ₂ .C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂	1585(s)	1075(s)	942(s)	935(s)	800(s)	650(m)	540(s)	450(m)	430(m)
4.	Mo ₂ O ₂ S ₂ [S ₂ P(OPh) ₂] ₂ .C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂	1595(s)	1065(s)	955(s)	940(m)	842(s)	655(s)	552(s)	470(m)	435(m)
5.	Mo ₂ O ₂ S ₂ [S ₂ P(OMe) ₂] ₂ .C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂	1600(s)	1010(s)	950(s)	920(m)	820(s)	645(m)	535(s)	450(m)	435(w)
6.	Mo ₂ O ₂ S ₂ [S ₂ P(OEt) ₂] ₂ .C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂	1595(s)	1050(s)	970(s)	940(m)	840(s)	650(s)	542(s)	445(m)	430(w)
7.	Mo ₂ O ₂ S ₂ [S ₂ P(OPr ⁱ) ₂] ₂ .C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂	1590(s)	1080(s)	950(s)	920(m)	800(s)	670(s)	545(s)	455(mw)	435(w)
8.	Mo ₂ O ₂ S ₂ [S ₂ P(OPh) ₂] ₂ .C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂	1600(s)	1040(s)	958(s)	930(m)	845(s)	665(s)	572(s)	480(mw)	446(w)

Key : s = strong, m = medium, w = weak.

strong band due to $\nu(\text{P}=\text{S})$ observed at 690–670 cm⁻¹ in the dialkyldithiophosphoric acids and their ammonium salts which is shifted to lower frequency²⁸ by about 25 cm⁻¹ in the corresponding bis(μ -sulphido)bis[$\{O, O$ -dialkyl(diphenyl)dithiophosphato}oxomolybdenum(ν)] complexes, is similarly shifted in 2,2'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline adducts of oxomolybdenum(ν) complexes, representing no change in the bonding patterns of the dithiophosphate moieties after adduct formation.

The bands present in the region 572–535 cm⁻¹ are assigned to $\nu(\text{P}-\text{S})$ asymmetric and symmetric vibration modes. The bands in the 480–425 cm⁻¹ region attributed

to $\nu(\text{Mo}-\text{S}_2-\text{Mo})$ asymmetric and $\nu(\text{Mo}-\text{S}_2-\text{Mo})$ symmetric vibrations.

Electronic absorption spectra :

The electronic spectra of these synthesized oxomolybdenum(ν) complexes are given in Table 3. The electronic spectra resemble those of other Mo₂O₂S₂²⁺ core contains complexes, show charge transfer transitions and intra-ligand transitions. It is possible that in the corresponding complexes a further $d-d$ transition is hidden by the tail of charge transfer transitions^{28,29}. A scrutiny of the table shows that the Mo₂O₂S₂²⁺ core containing complexes also show intra-ligand transitions (i.e. $n \rightarrow \sigma^*$,

Table 3. Some relevant electronic absorption spectral data [λ_{max} , nm (Å)] for the adducts of bis(μ -sulphido)bis[$\{O, O$ -dialkyldithiophosphato}oxomolybdenum(ν)] complexes with 2,2'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline

Sl. No.	Compd.	λ_{max} (nm)	Absorbance	Assignment
1.	Mo ₂ O ₂ S ₂ [S ₂ P(OMe) ₂] ₂ .C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂	372	0.31	Charge transfer transitions
		292(sh)	0.48	Intra-ligand transitions
2.	Mo ₂ O ₂ S ₂ [S ₂ P(OEt) ₂] ₂ .C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂	365	0.49	Charge transfer transitions
		310(sh)	0.12	Intra-ligand transitions
3.	Mo ₂ O ₂ S ₂ [S ₂ P(OPr ⁱ) ₂] ₂ .C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂	370	0.54	Charge transfer transitions
		299(sh)	1.20	Intra-ligand transitions
4.	Mo ₂ O ₂ S ₂ [S ₂ P(OPh) ₂] ₂ .C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂	362	0.51	Charge transfer transitions
		280(sh)	0.23	Intra-ligand transitions
5.	Mo ₂ O ₂ S ₂ [S ₂ P(OMe) ₂] ₂ .C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂	365	0.42	Charge transfer transitions
		290(sh)	0.41	Intra-ligand transitions
6.	Mo ₂ O ₂ S ₂ [S ₂ P(OEt) ₂] ₂ .C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂	352	0.18	Charge transfer transitions
		290(sh)	1.67	Intra-ligand transitions
7.	Mo ₂ O ₂ S ₂ [S ₂ P(OPr ⁱ) ₂] ₂ .C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂	370	0.37	Charge transfer transitions
		310(sh)	1.58	Intra-ligand transitions
8.	Mo ₂ O ₂ S ₂ [S ₂ P(OPh) ₂] ₂ .C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂	350	0.18	Charge transfer transitions
		285(sh)	0.31	Intra-ligand transitions

Table 4. ^1H NMR chemical shifts (δ ppm) for the adducts of bis(μ -sulphido)bis[$\{O, O$ -dialkyl(diphenyl)-dithiophosphato}oxomolybdenum(V) complexes with 2,2'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline^{a-d}

Sl. No.	Compound	OCH ₃ /OCH ₂ /OCH/OC ₆ H ₅	OC-CH ₃	Bipy/Phen
1.	Mo ₂ O ₂ S ₂ [S ₂ P(OCH ₃) ₂] ₂ .C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂	3.66 (6H, ds, <i>J</i> (PH) 17 Hz) 4.30 (6H, ds, <i>J</i> (PH) 17 Hz)	–	7.71–9.06 (8H, m)
2.	Mo ₂ O ₂ S ₂ [S ₂ P(OCH ₂ CH ₃) ₂] ₂ .C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂	3.97 (4H, dq, <i>J</i> (PH) 9.7, 7.2 Hz) 4.73 (4H, dq, <i>J</i> (PH) 9.7, 7.2 Hz)	1.31 (6H, t, <i>J</i> 7.0 Hz) 1.58 (6H, t, <i>J</i> 7.0 Hz)	7.76–9.07 (8H, m)
3.	Mo ₂ O ₂ S ₂ [S ₂ P{OCH(CH ₃) ₂ }] ₂ .C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂	4.38 (2H, m, <i>J</i> (PH) 12, 7.0 Hz) 5.36 (2H, m, <i>J</i> (PH) 12, 7.0 Hz)	1.30 (12H, d, <i>J</i> 6.4 Hz) 1.59 (12H, d, <i>J</i> 6.4 Hz)	7.72–9.02 (8H, m)
4.	Mo ₂ O ₂ S ₂ [S ₂ P(OC ₆ H ₅) ₂].C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂	6.99 (20H, s)	–	7.62–9.01 (8H, m)
5.	Mo ₂ O ₂ S ₂ [S ₂ P(OCH ₃) ₂] ₂ .C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂	3.65 (6H, ds, <i>J</i> (PH) 17 Hz) 4.28 (6H, ds, <i>J</i> (PH) 17 Hz)	–	7.72–9.08 (8H, m)
6.	Mo ₂ O ₂ S ₂ [S ₂ P(OCH ₂ CH ₃) ₂] ₂ .C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂	3.96 (4H, dq, <i>J</i> (PH) 9.6, 7.0 Hz) 4.74 (4H, dq, <i>J</i> (PH) 9.6, 7.0 Hz)	1.30 (6H, t, <i>J</i> 7.0 Hz) 1.58 (6H, t, <i>J</i> 7.0 Hz)	7.75–9.10 (8H, m)
7.	Mo ₂ O ₂ S ₂ [S ₂ P{OCH(CH ₃) ₂ }] ₂ .C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂	4.39 (2H, m, <i>J</i> (PH) 12, 7.0 Hz) 5.38 (2H, m, <i>J</i> (PH) 12, 7.0 Hz)	1.31 (12H, d, <i>J</i> 6.4 Hz) 1.59 (12H, d, <i>J</i> 6.4 Hz)	7.63–9.04 (8H, m)
8.	Mo ₂ O ₂ S ₂ [S ₂ P(OC ₆ H ₅) ₂].C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂	6.98 (20H, s)	–	7.64–9.02 (8H, m)

^aThe spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ and reported in ppm from MeSi. ^bNumber of protons and multiplicities are in parentheses (s = singlet; d = doublet; t = triplet; q = quartet; m = multiplet). ^cCoupling constants in Hz indicated by *J*(PH) and *J* for PH and HH coupling, respectively. ^dBoth *J*(HH) coupling constants have the value 7.0 Hz.

$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$) in the region 280–310 nm. Presence of intense bands in the region 350–372 nm is due to charge transfer transitions.

^1H NMR spectra :

Chemical shifts and integrated intensity ratio of protons on oxomolybdenum(V) complexes are set in Table 4. These spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ and DMSO-*d*₆ solutions at room temperature, illustrated peak patterns have comparable to the parent dithiophosphate derivatives with additional bands due to the base moieties in the aromatic region^{27,30}. The non-equivalence of the group attached to phosphorus is the primary feature of the ^1H NMR spectra. These adducts (1–8), have splitting patterns and relative intensities that are consistent with the solid state structures being maintained in solution. Thus, for example, the methyl groups in Mo₂O₂S₂[S₂P(OCH₃)₂]₂.C₁₂H₈N₂ are essentially identifiable in terms of first order spectra with the OCH₃ groups seen as two sets of doublets of singlets. Two sets arise from the non-equivalence of the OCH₃ groups and the values of the *J*(PH) and *J*(HH) coupling constants giving rise to the doublet of singlets are of the expected magnitude as obtained in the case of parent acid^{31,32}.

The ^1H NMR spectra of adducts of oxomolybdenum(V) complexes show that the change in the position of the

aromatic protons in the adducts of oxomolybdenum(V) complexes is more distinct and observed in both the directions. Thus, the *meta* protons in these cases are shifted downfield from 1.0–1.1 ppm and *ortho* protons are shifted upfield from 1.5–1.6 ppm. It is difficult to locate the peaks due to *para* protons with conviction.

In outlook of the above physico-chemical studies (IR, UV-Visible and ^1H NMR) for 2,2'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline adducts of bis(μ -sulphido)bis[$\{O, O$ -dialkyl(diphenyl)dithiophosphato}oxomolybdenum(V)] complexes, a hexa-coordinated octahedral structure is proposed for these adducts (Fig. 1 and Fig. 2). Altogether adducts of dithiophosphato moieties are bidentate in nature.

Experimental

All synthetic work was carried out under strictly anhydrous conditions. MoCl₅ was procured commercially from E. Merck. All solvents were dried by standard methods before use. Literature methods were used for the preparation of *O, O*-dialkyl and diphenyl dithiophosphoric acids³³ and for Mo₂O₂(ϕ -S₂)[S₂P(OR)₂]₂²⁴.

Analytical methods : Molybdenum was estimated by precipitation as molybdenum oxinate, MoO₂(C₉H₆ON)₂ and sulphur by gravimetrically as barium sulphate

Fig. 1. Proposed structure of 2,2'-bipyridyl adducts of $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2(\mu\text{-S}_2)[\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OR})_2]_2$.

Fig. 2. Proposed structure of 1,10-phenanthroline adducts of $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2(\mu\text{-S}_2)[\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OR})_2]_2$.

(Messenger's method), correspondingly. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer in KBr pellets in the range $4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Electronic spectra in the range $200\text{--}800\text{ nm}$ were recorded on UV-Visible spectrophotometer-119 in CH_2Cl_2 . ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on a Jeol FX 90Q spectrometer in CDCl_3 using TMS as an internal standard.

Synthesis of 2,2'-bipyridyl adducts of $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2(\phi\text{-S}_2)[\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OR})_2]_2$: Preparation of $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2(\phi\text{-S}_2)[\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OMe})_2]_2 \cdot \text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2$ (**1**); $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2(\phi\text{-S}_2)[\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OEt})_2]_2 \cdot \text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2$ (**2**); $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2(\phi\text{-S}_2)[\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OPr}^i)_2]_2 \cdot \text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2$ (**3**); $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2(\phi\text{-S}_2)[\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OPh})_2]_2 \cdot \text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2$ (**4**) :

To a solution of $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2(\phi\text{-S}_2)[\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OMe})_2]_2$ (0.42 g, 0.69 mmol) in benzene/*n*-hexane (1 : 2) a solution of 2,2'-bipyridyl [$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2$] (0.11 g, 0.69 mmol) in the same solvent was added dropwise in equimolar ratio with constant stirring. The solution turned from yellow to purple with precipitation on complete addition of 2,2'-bipyridyl solution. The precipitated 1 : 1 bipyridyl adducts were filtered off, washed with *n*-hexane and dried under reduced pressure to give $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2(\phi\text{-S}_2)[\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OMe})_2]_2 \cdot \text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2$ (**1**), dark purple solid. Similarly $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2(\phi\text{-S}_2)[\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OEt})_2]_2 \cdot \text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2$ (**2**), $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2(\phi\text{-S}_2)[\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OPr}^i)_2]_2 \cdot \text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2$ (**3**) and $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2(\phi\text{-S}_2)[\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OPh})_2]_2 \cdot \text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2$ (**4**) were also prepared.

$\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2(\phi\text{-S}_2)[\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OPr}^i)_2]_2 \cdot \text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2$ (**3**) and $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2(\phi\text{-S}_2)[\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OPh})_2]_2 \cdot \text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2$ (**4**) were also prepared.

Synthesis of 1,10-phenanthroline adducts of $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2(\phi\text{-S}_2)[\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OR})_2]_2$: Preparation of $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2(\phi\text{-S}_2)[\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OMe})_2]_2 \cdot \text{C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2$ (**5**); $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2(\phi\text{-S}_2)[\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OEt})_2]_2 \cdot \text{C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2$ (**6**); $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2(\phi\text{-S}_2)[\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OPr}^i)_2]_2 \cdot \text{C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2$ (**7**); $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2(\phi\text{-S}_2)[\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OPh})_2]_2 \cdot \text{C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2$ (**8**) :

To a solution of $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2(\phi\text{-S}_2)[\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OMe})_2]_2$ (0.29 g, 0.49 mmol) in benzene/*n*-hexane (1 : 2), a solution of 1,10-phenanthroline [$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$] (0.09 g, 0.49 mmol) in the same solvent was added in equimolar ratio with constant stirring. The solution turned from yellow to red with precipitation on complete addition of phenanthroline solution. The precipitated 1 : 1 phenanthroline adducts were filtered off, washed with *n*-hexane and dried under reduced pressure to give $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2(\phi\text{-S}_2)[\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OMe})_2]_2 \cdot \text{C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2$ (**5**), dark purple powdery solid. Similarly $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2(\phi\text{-S}_2)[\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OEt})_2]_2 \cdot \text{C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2$ (**6**), $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2(\phi\text{-S}_2)[\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OPr}^i)_2]_2 \cdot \text{C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2$ (**7**) and $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2(\phi\text{-S}_2)[\text{S}_2\text{P}(\text{OPh})_2]_2 \cdot \text{C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2$ (**8**) were prepared, dark purple powdery solid.

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